

Search For Potent Anthelmintics: Part III. S-(3-Benzoxazolonylmethyl or Benzoxazolthionylmethyl) Dithiocarbamates of Piperazine and Other Amines

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A number of S-(3-benzoxazol-2-onylmethyl or benzoxazol-2-thionylmethyl)-N-substituted dithiocarbamates were synthesised by the condensation of 3-chloromethyl benzoxazol-2-one or 3-chloromethyl benzoxazol-2-thione with various ammonium or sodium salts of dithiocarbamic acids derived from piperazine and other primary and secondary amines for studying their anthelmintic activity.

THE anthelmintic and pesticidal properties of dithiocarbamate derivatives¹⁻² have been reported very recently. A number of benzimidazole³⁻⁴ and benzoxazole⁵ derivatives have been screened against helminths in mice and have shown very promising results. Also the rhodanine derivative⁶⁻⁷ (1) possesses high anthelmintic activity.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.

(i) *Aryl ammonium dithiocarbamates*: were prepared from aromatic primary amine, carbon disulfide and ammonia according to the method described by

The benzoxazolonylmethyl or benzoxazolthionyl methyl moiety (2) present in the compounds reported by us in this paper is analogous to left half of the structure (1) of active rhodanine derivative. Keeping these facts in view, title compounds were synthesised with the hope that the S-substitution of benzoxazolonylmethyl or benzoxazolthionylmethyl group in dithiocarbamates of piperazines and other amines might confer on them considerably increased anthelmintic property.

In the present communication the benzoxazol-2-one or benzoxazol-2-thione, prepared from *o*-amino phenol was condensed with formaldehyde to give the corresponding 3-hydroxymethyl derivative. The latter was converted to 3-chloromethyl derivative by the modification of a procedure adopted earlier^{8,9}. The 3-chloromethyl-benzoxazol-2-one (or 2-thione) on condensation with sodium or ammonium salts of dithiocarbamic acids of piperazine and other amines in the presence of acetone yielded the desired substituted dithiocarbamates.

The pharmacological screening of these compounds is in progress and will be communicated in due course.

Vogel¹⁰. The sodium salts of dithiocarbamic acids of secondary amines were prepared from secondary amine, CS₂ and NaOH by following the same method¹⁰.

(ii) *Benzoxazol-2-one*: was synthesised by condensing *o*-aminophenol with urea by a reported procedure.¹¹

(iii) *Benzoxazol-2-thione*: It was prepared from *o*-aminophenol, KOH, and CS₂ by the procedure¹² reported earlier.

(iv) *3-Hydroxymethyl benzoxazol-2-one (or 2-thione)*: These were prepared from benzoxazol-2-one (or 2-thione) and formaldehyde according to published procedures.^{8,9,13}

(v) *3-Chloromethyl benzoxazol-2-one*: In a 250 ml two necked r.b. flask fitted with a dropping funnel, reflux condenser having a calcium chloride guard tube, 0.1 mole of 3-hydroxymethyl-benzoxazol-2-one and dry benzene (100 ml) were taken. PCl₃ (0.1 mole) was added dropwise from the dropping funnel with occasional shaking in 15 to 20 mins. The reaction mixture was then refluxed on a water bath for 4 hrs. The solvent and excess of PCl₃ were removed by distilling under vacuum. The residue was washed

TABLE I

Sl. No.	NRR'	X	m.p. °C	Molecular Formula	%N	
					Calc.	Found
1.	Anilino	O	150	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	8.86	8.74
2.	<i>p</i> -Toluidino	O	154	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	8.48	8.42
3.	<i>o</i> -Toluidino	O	178-180	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	8.48	8.26
4.	<i>p</i> -Phenylanilino	O	208-209	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	7.16	7.04
5.	<i>m</i> -Chloroanilino	O	120	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	7.98	7.92
6.	<i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	O	214-216	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	7.98	7.88
7.	<i>p</i> -Anisidino	O	164-166	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	8.09	8.00
8.	Anilino	S	129-130	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS ₃	8.43	8.31
9.	<i>p</i> -Phenyl anilino	S	200-203	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS ₃	6.86	6.91
10.	<i>p</i> -Chloro anilino	S	165-166	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ OS ₃	7.63	7.58
11.	<i>m</i> -Chloro anilino	S	220-221	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ OS ₃	7.63	7.66
12.	Dimethyl amino	O	170-172	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	10.44	10.31
13.	Diethyl amino	O	85	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	9.45	9.50
14.	Dibenzyl amino	O	103-105	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	6.66	6.62
15.	Dimethyl amino	S	132-134	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS ₃	9.85	9.81
16.	Diethyl amino	S	105-108	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS ₃	8.97	8.76
17.	Pyrrolidino	O	152	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	9.52	9.61
18.	Morpholino	O	155-157	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	9.03	9.21
19.	Piperidino	O	131-132	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	9.09	9.18
20.	Pyrrolidino	S	188-190	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS ₃	9.03	9.12
21.	Morpholino	S'	165	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S ₃	8.58	8.66
22.	Piperidino	S'	220-222	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS ₃	8.64	8.45

TABLE 2

Sl.No.	Y	X	m.p. °C	Mol. formula	%N	
					Calc.	Found
1.		O	247-249	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	10.52	10.41
2.		S	248-250	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ S ₆	9.92	9.96
3.		O	126-128	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	8.88	8.84

with cold water and recrystallised from benzene. Yield 80%, m.p. 153°-54° (Lit.⁸ m.p. 154.5°). Found : N, 7.66%; Calc. for C₈H₆ClNO₂ : N, 7.62%.

(vi) 3-Chloromethyl-benzoxazol-2-thione : It was prepared similarly from 3-hydroxy methyl benzoxazol-2-thione. Yield 80%, m.p. 142°-43° (Lit.⁹ m.p. 141°-45°). Found : N, 7.11%; Calc. for C₈H₆ClNOS : N, 7.01%.

(vii) *S*-(3-Benzoxazol-2-onylmethyl)-*N*-phenyl dithiocarbamate : In a 250 ml r.b. flask, 3-chloromethyl benzoxazol-2-one (0.01 mole), phenyl ammonium dithiocarbamate (0.01 mole) and acetone (25 ml) were

taken and the mixture stirred vigorously for half an hour. The contents of the flask were then refluxed on a water bath for 15 mins. The solvent was distilled off and the residue washed with warm water (about 50°-60°). The solid thus obtained was recrystallised from acetone.

Adopting the above procedure, different dithiocarbamate derivatives were synthesised from 3-chloromethyl-benzoxazol-2-one and ammonium or sodium salts of dithiocarbamic acids derived from piperazine and other primary or secondary amines. The compounds obtained were recrystallised from

acetone or ethanol and the yield varied between 60 to 70%. The elemental analysis and m.p. of prepared compounds are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

(viii) *S*-(3-Benzoxazol-2-thionylmethyl)-*N*-substituted dithiocarbamates: Following the method described previously these were prepared by condensing 3-chloromethyl-benzoxazo 1-2-thione with sodium or ammonium salts of various dithiocarbamic acids. The compounds thus obtained in a yield of 50 to 55% are given in Tables 1 and 2.

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